

A Prospective Hospital Based Study to Assess the Correlation Between Glycemic Control, Lipid Profile and C-Reactive Protein in Adults with Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus

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Abstract

Introduction: Onset of type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM) at early age heralds many years of disease and an increased risk that the full range of both microvascular and macrovascular complications will occur when affected individuals are still relatively young. Thus, further generations may be burdened with morbidity and mortality at the height of their productivity, potentially affecting workforce, and healthcare systems of countries across the world.

Methods: Total 50 patients with T2DM reporting to Nalanda Medical College & Hospital, Patna were included in the study, in whom CRP levels were estimated by using commercially available kits and correlated with HbA1C and other risk factors of coronary artery disease. Follow-up was done on 10 patients who were not on statin therapy with repeat HbA1C and CRP.

Results: This study showed that both HbA1C and CRP levels had reduced significantly in follow-up patients after putting them on treatment ($p < 0.05$). It was also found that lowers the HbA1C, lower was the CRP. A positive correlation was found between HbA1C and CRP ($p < 0.05$).

Conclusion: A positive correlation was found between serum CRP and HbA1C in the initial group and in the follow-up patients, showing that CRP levels lowers with better glycemic control and correlates with dyslipidemia profile.

Keywords: C-reactive protein, Glycemic control, Hemoglobin A1C, Type 2 diabetes mellitus

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Introduction

In India, nearly 75% of T2DM patients have the first-degree family history. The lifetime risk of developing the disease is about 40% in offspring of one parent with

T2DM and the risk approaches to 70% if both parents have diabetes. In terms of sibling relative risk, a first-degree relative (FDR) of a patient with T2DM has a

threefold increased risk of developing the disease. [1] It is found that Indians have 45% positive family history of diabetes as compared to 38% of the Europeans. [2] Lipid metabolism in T2DM is modulated by a series of factors among which, the degree of glycemic control and the presence of insulin resistance (IR) are the two most important factors. Diabetic dyslipidemia is a complex cluster of potentially atherogenic lipid and lipoprotein changes. Increased plasma triglycerides (TGs), especially very high-density lipoprotein (VLDL),

TG, and low concentration of high-density lipoprotein cholesterol (HDL-C), preponderance of small, dense low-density lipoprotein (LDL) and excessive postprandial lipemia are the main components of diabetic dyslipidemia. [3]

Patients with T2DM have a two to four-fold higher risk of cardiovascular events. The progression of coronary artery disease appears faster when compared with non-diabetic patients. [4] Since inflammation is believed to have a role in the pathogenesis of cardiovascular events, measurement of markers of inflammation has been proposed as a method to improve the prediction of the risk of these events. [5]

C-reactive protein is the most reliable marker of inflammation. [6] CRP is produced by hepatocytes largely under the regulatory control of inflammatory cytokines, including IL-6, TNF- α . [5]

Diabetes exposure can be characterized by the level of glycosylated hemoglobin (HbA1C) which is an accurate, precise measure of chronic glycemic levels and correlates well with risk of diabetic complications. C-reactive protein and glycated hemoglobin (HbA1C) are established risk factors for the development of cardiovascular diseases. [5]

Diabetes mellitus (DM) with its complication has become the most important and challenging contemporary

health problem. Globally, the estimated number of adults with diabetes in 2007 was 246 million and 380 million adults worldwide will have diabetes by 2025. India has 41 million diabetics and this number is expected to increase to 70 million by 2025. [7] Over the past 30 years, the status of diabetes has changed from being considered as a mild disorder of the elderly to one of the major causes of morbidity and mortality affecting the youth and middle-aged people. [8] Onset of type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM) at early age heralds many years of disease and an increased risk that the full range of both microvascular and macrovascular complications will occur when affected individuals are still relatively young. Thus, further generations may be burdened with morbidity and mortality at the height of their productivity, potentially affecting workforce, and healthcare systems of countries across the world. [9]

CRP is a possible risk factor for the development of type 2 diabetes mellitus. The glycemic control is related to CRP, but the relationship has yet to be elucidated. [5]

Materials and Methods

This was a hospital-based prospective study comprised of 50 patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus reporting to Nalanda Medical College & Hospital, Patna, Bihar, India over a period of one year.

Inclusion criteria: Inclusion criteria were the patients above 30 years with fasting venous blood glucose value equal or more than 100 mg/dl and postprandial glucose >140 mg/dl were included in the study.

Exclusion criteria: Exclusion criteria were patients on statins, thiazolidinediones (TZDs), and anti-inflammatory drugs that are known to reduce CRP levels excluded from the study. Patients with heart failure, acute febrile illness, renal, hepatic and malignant disorders, chronic illnesses, asymptomatic infections, type 1 diabetes, gestational diabetes, alcoholism,

pancreatitis, and other endocrinal disorders, those on diuretic therapy, amino-glycosides and smokers were also excluded from the study.

Informed consent was taken from the patients. Detailed history, physical examination, which includes height, weight, body mass index (kg/m²), were measured. Resting pulse rate, blood pressure, body temperature was recorded. FBS and PPBS, CRP (immunoturbidimetric method), and HbA1C (ion exchange chromatography

Results:

using HPLC) lipid profile samples were drawn at entry and at subsequent follow-up with a minimum gap of 3 months. Patients were put on OHA/insulin for control of blood sugar along with dietary control and exercise.

Statistical analysis: Statistical analysis was done using SPSS package and MS excel. Student's 't' test and X² test was used. Pearson correlation and p values were calculated. P values <0.05 was considered to be significant.

Table 1: CRP in males and females.

CRP	Number	Mean
Males	32	1.2817
Females	18	0.8820
Total	50	2.1637

In this study of 50 patients, 32 patients were males, and 18 were females. There was no significant difference between male and female patients (p>0.05)

Table 2: Age distribution and CRP and HbA1C.

Age	Number	HbA1C	CRP
30-40	5	11.39	1.61
40-50	8	11.52	2.28
50-60	20	10.20	1.42
60-70	15	10.19	0.8
>70	2	7.5	0

Patients between ages 50-60 years were 20 with mean HbA1C and CRP of 10.20 and 1.42 respectively. There was no significance between different age groups in this study (p>0.05)

Table 3: CRP and BMI.

BMI	Number	CRP
<18	1	1.20
18-23	21	1.10
23-25	33	1.20
25-30	7	1.40
>30	2	1.20

In this study of 50 patients, patients with BMI <18 was 1 with mean CRP of 1.20. BMI between 23-25 were 33 with mean CRP of 1.20, BMI 25-30 were 7 with mean CRP of 1.40. There was no significant correlation between CRP and BMI in this study.

Table 4: FBS with HbA1C and CRP.

FBS	Number	HbA1C
<100	3	9.10

100-200	20	9.32
200-300	17	11.39
>300	10	12.81

Patients with FBS Of 100 was 3 with HbA1C were 9.10, between 100-200 were 20, between 200-300 were 17, >300 were 10 had HbA1C of 9.32, 11.39, 12.81 respectively. FBS and HbA1C were directly correlated.

Table 5: PPBS with HbA1C and CRP.

PPBS	Number	HbA1C	CRP
140-200	8	9.62	0.49
200-300	15	12.34	0.55
300-400	19	11.67	2.10
400-500	7	14.73	3.5
>500	1	16.81	3.7

In this study of 50 patients, PPBS was correlated to HbA1C and CRP.

Table 6: CRP and total cholesterol.

LDL	Number	CRP
<60	6	1.91
60-80	17	0.98
80-100	15	1.75
100-120	7	0.79
120-140	1	1.42
>140	4	2.80

There was no significant correlation between CRP and LDL cholesterol ($p>0.05$)

Table 7: CRP and LDL cholesterol.

LDL	Number	CRP
<60	7	1.87
60-80	18	0.90
80-100	13	1.88
100-120	8	0.98
120-140	1	1.67
>140	3	2.98

There was no significant correlation between CRP and LDL cholesterol ($p>0.05$)

Table 8: CRP and HDL cholesterol.

HDL	Number	CRP
0-20	7	2.89
20-40	14	1.45
40-60	26	1.16
>60	3	1.11

In this study of 50 patients, HDL cholesterol was compared with CRP. Patients with HDL cholesterol between 0-20 were 7, between 20-40 were 14, between 40-60 were 26 and HDL cholesterol >60 was 3 with mean CRP levels of 2.89, 1.45, 1.16, 1.11, respectively. There was a negative correlation between HDL cholesterol and CRP

Table 9: CRP and triglycerides.

Triglycerides	Number	CRP
100-200	31	0.74
200-300	10	0.81
300-400	4	1.62
400-500	4	2.48
>500	1	2.22

In this study of 50 patients, triglyceride levels were compared with CRP. Patients with triglyceride levels between 100-200 were 31, between 200-300 were 10, between 300-400 were 4, between 400-500 was 4 and with levels >500 were 1 with mean CRP levels of 0.74, 0.81, 1.62, 2.48, 2.22, respectively. There was significant positive correlation between CRP and triglyceride levels ($p < 0.05$)

Table 10: CRP and HbA1C.

HbA1C	Number	CRP
<7	4	0.47
7-9	10	0.54
9-10	11	2.72
>10	25	3.10

In this study of 50 patients, patients with HbA1C <7 were 4 between 7-9 were 10, between 9-10 were 11, HbA1C >10 were 25 with mean CRP of 0.47, 0.54, 2.72, 3.10, respectively. There was significant correlation between CRP and HbA1C ($p < 0.05$)

Table 11: HbA1C and CRP of 50 initial and 10 follow-up cases.

	HbA1c	HbA1c	CRP	CRP
	Initial (50)	Follow-up (10)	Initial (50)	Follow-up (10)
Mean	8.7291	8.68	1.5282	0.48
SD	1.6820	1.69	0.9776	0.55
P value		0.0001		0.0003

The mean HbA1C of 50 patients initially was 8.7 ± 1.6 , and the mean CRP was 1.5 ± 0.9776 . A follow-up of 10 cases was done on patients who were not on statin

Discussion:

Type 2 diabetes mellitus is a major risk factor for death, and numerous nonfatal complications. C-reactive protein, a marker of systemic inflammation, is emerging as an independent risk factor for cardiovascular disease and has been linked

therapy. On follow-up, the mean HbA1C of 10 cases had reduced to 8.68 ± 1.69 ($p < 0.05$) and mean CRP of those 10 patients reduced to 0.48 ± 0.55 ($p < 0.05$)

to an increased risk of thrombotic events. CRP levels are higher in people with diabetes compared to those without. Not much is known whether CRP in people with diabetes is related to the level of glycemic control. [5]

King and others in unadjusted analyses, demonstrated that a higher HbA1C is significantly associated with a higher CRP levels. [10] This study showed that a rise in HbA1C, higher glycemic levels significantly correlated with increasing values of CRP. Steven et al found that the correlation between the reduction in LDL cholesterol and CRP levels was weak but significant in the group as a whole. [11] In this study, there was no significant correlation between CRP and LDL cholesterol.

Takiko et al showed that CRP negatively correlated with HDL cholesterol which were similar to the findings observed in this study. [12] Ana et al found that his-CRP levels were positively correlated with triglycerides. [13] This study also showed a positive correlation similar to other studies.

There is growing evidence supporting the concept that chronic, low-grade, inflammatory states may have a pathogenic role in IR. Several studies have shown that proinflammatory cytokines and acute-phase reactants are correlated with measures of IR, BMI, waist circumference, circulating TG, and HDL cholesterol concentration. [14]

Inflammatory cytokines, such as tumor necrosis factor- α (TNF- α) and interleukin-6 (IL-6), have been linked to IR, and their expression is increased in adipose tissue. [15]

Conclusion:

A positive correlation was found between serum CRP and HbA1C in the initial group and in the follow-up patients, showing that CRP levels lowers with better glycemic control and correlates with dyslipidemia profile.

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